

Editorial

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Web-Based Payroll System for Fixed-Term Employees

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Abstract: Web-based Payroll System for Fixed Term Employees is a simple web-based attendance system that was developed for manufacturing industries. It was specifically designed to calculate the payroll of fixed-term employees whose wages were calculated based on the number of hours worked at an agreed amount paid per hour. The significance of this application is to be able to determine the actual amount to be paid to each employee devoid of cheating by making use of a biometric machine to capture the actual time employees come to work and the time they leave. Many organisations nowadays are battling for survival because of fraud perpetrated by employees. This study helps to bridge this gap by helping organisations to manage employee productivity and prevent cheating as it cannot be manipulated. The Software Development Kit (SDK) of the digitalPersona fingerprint scanner was integrated with the system using J-Query. The fingerprint scanner communicates with the system using the serial port of a computer system. Also, J-Query was made to interact with the fingerprint scanner, scan the print signature of the employee and save it in the database using MySQL. It is from the database that attendance is estimated while VB.NET and PHP were used to develop the payroll system. The System Usability Scale (SUS) was used to evaluate the program after ten respondents were sampled and given questionnaires to fill out.

Key Words: Attendance, Biometric, Fingerprint, Employee, Software, Payroll

I. INTRODUCTION

The term “payroll” refers to the number of workers that get compensation from a company (R. Patra & Teja, 2023; Yulisfan *et al.*, 2021). Even though, most companies generally use the term to refer to the money that is paid to the employees or the records that shows how much each employee has collected. Payroll may also refer to the company, department, or software which is used to process paycheques and taxes or to the process of calculating and distributing employee paycheques. Processing payroll is a very important function of any business which necessitates an understanding of current regulations, detailed tax knowledge to ensure proper withholding and filing, and a highly organised system that can be relied upon to pay each employee the right amount of money. For many organisations, using payroll systems can help to mitigate stress and minimise errors.

A. Payroll Deductions and Processing

Payroll deductions include many different items, including:

- i. Federal income taxes
- ii. Social Security taxes
- iii. State income taxes
- iv. Local tax withholdings
- v. Health insurance

Patra and Teja (2023) state that Payroll must be processed repeatedly, that is on a weekly or monthly basis and at such times, it must be accurate. Since payroll is the single largest expense for most companies, it is very important that payroll is processed in a way that is efficient and can be relied upon. There are several options for processing payroll. Processing payroll manually is an inexpensive option but can be manipulated. The Internal Revenue Service (IRS) provides tax tables used in calculating withholdings, but voluntary deductions must be figured out as well. Keeping good records, organising information, and ensuring consistent accuracy may be more difficult when payroll is processed manually. Outsourcing payroll is expensive but may save labour time and prevent errors. A payroll company will take care of all taxes and other payroll issues, ensuring that it is accurate and reliable and may also be able to help answer questions that may arise. Payroll software is a good middle-of-the-road option, affordable for most companies and simple to use so it saves some labour time. Many different payroll software options enable the selection of the amount of assistance needed with payroll. Since payroll is still taken care of in-house with payroll software, it may be easier to make changes and retrieve data, which may also be a bonus over payroll outsourcing.

B. Employment Types

This is like an agreement between an employer and an employee. There are several ways staff can be employed, with each having peculiar arrangements for wages and leave entitlements. The different employment types include full-time employees, part-time employees, casual employees, fixed-term or contract employees, apprentices and trainees. While full-time employees work regularly for an average of 38 hours per week, part-time employees usually work less than 38 hours per week and generally have regular hours. Part-time employees receive the same wages and conditions as full-time employees on a proportionate or pro-rata basis, according to the number of hours worked. However, the conditions are different for other employees type. For example, casual employees are engaged on an irregular basis according to business demands while fixed-term or contract employees can be engaged for an agreed length of time to perform a specific task or work on a particular project or replace an employee on leave, for example. Fixed-term employees can work full or part-time and, in most cases, do not enjoy the benefits enjoyed by permanent staff. It is outsourced to a contractor who takes care of their wages and is paid either on a weekly or monthly basis.

Furthermore, apprentices and trainees are working towards a nationally recognised qualification or working towards having a certain knowledge about the job. They must be formally registered, usually through a contract between a registered training provider, the employee, and the employer. Apprentices and trainees get paid according to their award or

registered agreement. In addition, one can pay piece rates or commission payments to employees in certain circumstances. This means that they get paid based on the results they achieve instead of an hourly or weekly pay rate. This is applied majorly in sales where an employee's pay will be based on a percentage of the total number of goods sold. Requirements vary for this arrangement depending on which industrial relations system one belongs to.

C. Attendance Timing

Most organisations across the world run a 40-hour shift/week for employees which is an 8-hour/day shift, while some run a 45-hour shift/week. Any extra hour is calculated as overtime. While some organisations run 3 shifts/day which is not quite common here in Nigeria, the majority of the organisations here run 2 shifts/day day and night. The day shift runs from 8am to 5pm and the night shift runs from 8pm to 5am. In some situations, however, workers in production lines where machines run 24 hours each day can work from 7am to 7pm while those on night shift work from 7pm to 7am. Overtime is simply an additional number of hours worked by an employee daily. If an employee is supposed to work from 8am to 5pm and such employee ended up working from 8am to 6pm, the extra one hour is overtime and any amount agreed between the employer and employee is to be paid as overtime will be paid to such employee.

This study focuses on developing a hybridised web-based biometric system for the attendance and payroll of fixed term employees in a manufacturing environment. Specifically, the study intends to develop a web-based attendance system, develop a web-based payroll system, develop a database to store the attendance and payroll systems, and integrate and evaluate the systems for robust performance. The study deals mainly with the payroll of fixed term employees in a soap manufacturing company in the south-western part of Nigeria. It does not cover permanent employees.

Due to the use of manual processes or minimal adoption of technology in attendance and payroll processing, an avenue where fixed term employees cheat employers via various means is created. For example, conniving with HR staff or with one another by helping one another to sign the attendance register when they are not at their jobs. Solving this challenge is necessary. The widespread prevalence, adoption and usage of biometrics have opened its adoption in the workplace for attendance and payroll of employees.

D. Problem Statement

Years back, industries and institutions take attendance manually, which is time and paper-consuming, all in the process of keeping records. The first attendance machine is very simple and works by workers inserting an attendance paper or a timesheet into a machine with the time of insertion printed on the timesheet. This is also time-consuming and causes long queues while doing attendance. Also, the data on the timesheet is processed manually by HR to do Payroll. Nowadays, various automated attendance systems are used for attendance taking and even remotely. However, with the existing systems on attendance and payroll and with it not being implemented for fixed term employees, there are lots of fraudulent manipulations in some companies in Nigeria. If this is not checked, it will lead to the collapse of many organisations in a country where there is unemployment already. Hence, the need to have an efficient system that

saves time and pays for the exact number of hours of work done by an employee.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

Singh *et al.* (2017) proposed a web-based leave and payroll system. The system integrates with other systems using APIs. In such an establishment where it is implemented, new features can be added which might not have been there at the beginning when the system is being deployed and it will not affect the integrity of the system. It is also deployed in a way that it will automatically work and link with the biometric attendance system.

In the work of Rahman *et al.* (2017), they proposed an automated system. The system comprises six different modules. The modules range from the employee management system to the employee attendance management system, employee leave management system, employee performance management system, employee payroll system and employee monitoring system. The system is used by an admin, an operator and the employees. Each has separate access to the system according to what is required of them.

Tharanya and SenthilRaja (2020) introduced a web-based smart attendance and payroll system where employee details are captured into a database and each employee is assigned a unique employee number. An admin logs into the system to log an employee in and out daily. This step captures workers' time and provides a day-to-day activity of time records as a report or for further usage such as the monthly wage calculation by finance department programming attendance management.

In the work of Prasad *et al.* (2019), each employee gets a secured identification number that they use to authenticate, which along with other information like the coordinates and images are saved on their smartphones that run on Android, which also have the required APK Files installed on it. The employees log into the system on their smartphones with their credentials and take an image for security purposes. Employees are required to turn on their GPS on their Android smartphones as the process won't go if it is turned off. Each employee's smartphone on getting to work connects to an access point WIFI and does attendance and the records are used to calculate their pay.

Patra *et al.* (2021) introduced a system that collects the attendance of workers with a biometric scanner. The collected attendance data is at the same time uploaded on the cloud. This data can be accessed by both the organisation and workers by making use of their respective applications. The organisation will be able to work on the employee's data with the aid of attendance taking and all other things performed in the software application to calculate Payroll.

Kimani and Nyatuka (2018) used barcodes to authenticate users for attendance. Users scan the barcode on their pass ID in and out, which serves as input for the payroll calculation. PHP, MySQL, HTML and notepad++ were used as tools, and software prototyping methodology was used.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

Every system has its way of identifying hardware using the

hardware's unique ID. Figure 1 shows the system design under discussion.

- WordPress was installed on the system for the front-end and back-end program design for web applications. Sublime text was also installed to write the PHP, CMS, and jQuery codes. PersonaDigita Fingerprint device and API were installed on the system to enable smooth communication between the fingerprint scanner and the software.
- VB.NET framework was installed on the PC. This was used to develop the standalone system application. The standalone system application communicates with the web application.
- Xamp server application was installed on the PC. Xamp was used to create the MqSQL application stand as an offline server for the program to be executed on it. It is compatible with WordPress and PHP.
- The codes were compiled, test run and deployed to WordPress.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The system was implemented in a manufacturing company in Nigeria. The company employs the services of consultants

in the recruitment and management of fixed term employees. The user's attendance records from biometrics were used in generating the payroll.

A. System Interface

The System interface opens when the payroll program is launched. On the interface, there are seven buttons as seen in Figure 2. It is on this interface that the admin logs in to the program, new employee fingerprints are captured, and employees also clock in and clock out. Before users can clock into the program, the admin has to log in to secure the program. After the admin login, new users' fingerprints must be captured and saved into the database before being allowed to clock in and out according to the shift schedule using the fingerprint scanner. Figure 2 shows the interface where a new employee is registered. The payroll dashboard is presented in Figure 3. It opens after the admin logs in to the program. In the payroll dashboard, one can navigate to attendance. Attendance was captured when users clock in with their registered fingerprints in the morning and clocked out after work. The attendance dashboard shows the time employees come in and out, the list of employees and other vital information relating to attendance.

Figure 1: System Design of the System

Figure 2: Control Dashboard of the System

Figure 3: Payroll Dashboard of the System

B. Shift Schedule

These are a set of rules that govern the resumption of work, closing at work, and overtime. Some organisations run 3 shifts, some 2 shifts and some 1 shift. In this program, we make use of 2 shifts from 8am to 5pm (morning shift) and 8pm to 5am (night shift). Any additional hours worked are overtime, which is added to the total amount for a day's work. Figure 4 shows the screenshot of the schedule.

C. Payroll Component

These are the required information needed to generate the payroll. We present a detailed explanation of what they mean as regards the computation of the payroll of a fixed-term employee ranging from the hourly pay, overtime pay, gross pay and the government tax, which is a mandatory deduction accruing to the government and deducted from the monthly pay of each employee.

Figure 4: Screenshot of Shift Schedule of Fixed-Term Employees in a Soap Factory

Figure 5: Screenshot of Payroll of Fixed-Term Employees in a Soap Factory

Hourly Pay: This is how much an employee is entitled to collect per hour. If an employee is placed on a 200 naira per hour pay, such employee working on an 8-hour shift will earn 1,600 naira per day.

Overtime Pay: The stipulated number of hours worked per day is 8 hours and per week is 40 hours. Any employee whose working period exceeds the stipulated number of hours backed by law is entitled to overtime pay. The overtime pay is calculated and added to the gross pay which an employee is entitled to at the end of the month. In the past, overtime pay was calculated and paid separately to avoid it being taxed. But nowadays, with government directives, overtime pay is added to gross pay and taxed accordingly.

Gross Pay: This is the total amount an employee earns at the end of the month before deductions. An employee who for example is on a 200 naira per hour per day earns 1,600 naira per day. If he works Monday through Friday, it becomes 8,000 naira and if it's 4 weeks in the month, 8,000 naira multiplied by 4 will give us 32,000 naira as the gross pay.

Deductions: For fixed-term employees earning from 40,000 naira and above per month, a 2% personal income tax is deducted from their salary per month. Therefore, if an employee earns 40,000 naira in a month, 2% of 40,000 naira is 800 naira. Such an employee at the end of the month will earn 39,200 naira. After the tax deduction, admin charges are also deducted. If 3,000 naira is fixed as admin charges, 3,000 naira will be deducted from 39,200 which gives us 36,200 as

the net pay. But for employees earning below 40,000 naira per month, the deduction will only be the 3,000 naira admin charges.

Pay Schedule: The input to the program comes from the fingerprint scanner. It captures for each employee their sign-in and sign-out time, which calculates the number of hours worked in a day plus overtime, if any. This calculation gives the gross pay for a month, and the net pay for the same month after all necessary deductions have been made. Below is a payroll of employees from June 6, 2022, to August 5, 2022, based on the number of times the employees were present at work. The various tabs and icons on the interface are explained below.

Date: This shows the period of the payroll i.e., from one day of the month to another.

Employee Name: This is the name of an employee.

Employee ID: This is a unique ID that the program assigns to each employee.

Gross: This is the total amount of money accruing to an employee at the end of a particular period.

Deductions: Deductions are the total of the admin charges and tax. Deductions go to Jemeco Nigeria Ltd for their administrative duties while Tax goes to the government.

Cash Advance: This is the money given to employees in the form of a small loan that will be deducted from the employee pay at the end of a particular period.

Net Pay: This is the take-home of the employees. It is the amount left for the employee after deductions have been made.

The sum of what the recruitment consultant pays to all employees for a particular period can be seen and printed as shown in Figure 7.

Payslip: For clarity, employees are expected to know what they get and how the figures were arrived at. A payslip contains all the necessary information as regards how much was paid and how much was deducted. This can be printed out and given to each employee at the end of a particular pay period. An example is shown in Figure 8.

Employee Name	Employee ID	Gross	Deductions	Cash Advance	Net Pay
.		0.00	3,250.00	0.00	-3,250.00
Ajayi, Seun	BJV876510243	9,670.00	3,250.00	0.00	6,420.00
Ajibade, Olalekan	POZ359201867	16,015.00	3,250.00	0.00	12,765.00
Akinyele, Olawale	FSD549120736	10,756.67	3,250.00	0.00	7,506.67
Anthony, Adebayo	ABC123456789	3,883.33	3,250.00	0.00	633.33
Jimoh, Adewale	LRH076548231	8,123.33	3,250.00	0.00	4,873.33
Sunday, Temiloluwa	GPW569017342	10,763.33	3,250.00	0.00	7,513.33

Figure 6: Screenshot of Payroll Report of Fixed-Term Employees in a Soap Factory

Employee Name	Employee ID	Net Pay
.		-3,250.00
Ajayi, Seun	BJV876510243	6,420.00
Ajibade, Olalekan	POZ359201867	12,765.00
Akinyele, Olawale	FSD549120736	7,506.67
Anthony, Adebayo	ABC123456789	633.33
Jimoh, Adewale	LRH076548231	4,873.33
Sunday, Temiloluwa	GPW569017342	7,513.33
Total		36,461.67

Figure 7: Screenshot of the total amount payable to Employees for a period in a Soap Factory

Figure 8: Screenshot of Employee Payslip in a Soap Factory

V. EVALUATION

The program was evaluated by using the System Usability Scale (SUS). The usability of a system takes the level of satisfaction, effectiveness and efficiency into consideration (Sakpere *et al.*, 2017). In SUS, a score of above 68 means that the program is usable while a score of below 68 means that there are some inhibitions and there's a need to modify the program. The score was calculated based on the user's response to the use of the program (Pal & Vanijja, 2020; Vlachogianni & Tselios, 2022).

A. Distribution of Respondents by Employment Type

Ten employees were selected while evaluating the program. The respondents were selected according to their employment type and their interaction with the program. They were drawn majorly from the records of a recruitment consultant that manages the fixed-term employees employed by the soap factory and from the permanent staff in the soap factory.

Table 1: Respondents' Distribution by Employment Type

Employment Type	Size
Fixed-Term	8
Full Staff	2
Total	10

B. Distribution of Respondents' Statements on Attendance Timing and Payroll

Ten questions were formulated. The questions were formed based on attendance timing and payroll. The questions were formulated in relation to the research objectives as shown in Table 2.

C. Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Questions

In Table 3, the number of respondents was tabulated against each question according to their responses. Ten questions were asked of the respondents. The sum of the total response on each column against each question is ten, which is equivalent to the ten respondents.

Table 2: Respondents' Statements on Attendance and Payroll

S/N	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Fingerprint takes less time to do Attendance					
2	Fingerprint Biometrics is better than manual					
3	Attendance is easy to capture with Biometrics					
4	Fingerprint Biometrics gives accurate time in and time out					
5	Biometrics clocking makes employee timing easy to audit					
6	Biometrics is the best input for payroll calculation					
7	Biometrics gives accurate data for payroll					
8	Biometrics gives accurate overtime data					
9	Biometrics makes payroll easy to calculate					
10	Biometrics Clocking makes payroll process to be faster					

Table 3: Respondents' Answers to Questions

S/N	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Fingerprint takes less time to do Attendance				2	8
2	Fingerprint Biometrics is better than manual				2	8
3	Attendance is easy to capture with Biometrics	1			2	7
4	Fingerprint Biometrics gives accurate time in and time out	1			4	5
5	Biometrics clocking makes employee timing easy to audit				3	7
6	Biometrics is the best input for payroll calculation	2			4	4
7	Biometrics gives accurate data for payroll				2	8
8	Biometrics gives accurate overtime data				2	8
9	Biometrics makes payroll easy to calculate	1			2	7
10	Biometrics Clocking makes payroll process to be faster				5	5

Table 4: Respondents' Point Numbers for Questions

S/N	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Fingerprint takes less time to do Attendance				8	40
2	Fingerprint Biometrics is better than manual				8	40
3	Attendance is easy to capture with Biometrics	1			8	35
4	Fingerprint Biometrics gives accurate time in and time out	1			16	25
5	Biometrics clocking makes employee timing easy to audit				12	35
6	Biometrics is the best input for payroll calculation	2			16	20
7	Biometrics gives accurate data for payroll				8	40
8	Biometrics gives accurate overtime data				8	40
9	Biometrics makes payroll easy to calculate	1			8	35
10	Biometrics Clocking makes payroll process to be faster				20	25

D. System Usability Scale (SUS) for the Program

The System Usability Scale does not tell the specific problem but gives a pointer to where the problem is. The average scale score is 68 and anything less than 68 points to the fact that there's a need for modifications. Using the system usability scale, respondents will rank each question from 1 to 5 based on how much they agree with the statement they are reading, where 5 means they agree, 4 means they agree, 3 means neutral, 2 means disagree and 1 means they disagree totally.

Using the first statement in Table 3 above as an example where 2 people agreed and 8 people strongly agreed, 2 multiplied by 4 equals 8 and 8 multiplied by 5 equals 40 as seen in the first statement in Table 4. For each of the odd-numbered questions, 1 was subtracted from the score and for each of the even-numbered questions, 5 was subtracted from their value. These new values for all odd-numbered questions were added to get X while the new values for all even-numbered questions were added to get Y. The new figures of X and Y were added and multiplied by 2.5.

From Table 4 above:

$$X = 47 + 43 + 46 + 47 + 43 = 226$$

$$Y = -43 - 37 - 33 - 43 - 40 = -196$$

$$X + Y = 226 - 196 = 30$$

$$30 \times 2.5 = 75$$

The average System Usability Scale score is 68. Since the score derived is 75, above 68, then the application's usability is acceptable. Going by the result obtained in evaluating the

system, the usability assessment measurement characteristics have been achieved by its:

- Effectiveness – users were able to achieve their objective.
- Efficiency – minimal effort and resources are expended to achieve the objectives.
- Satisfaction – users were satisfied using the system.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research proves that the problem of ghost workers can be solved using technology and the fraud being carried out in public and private establishments in Nigeria can stop with the use of biometrics. Also, the era where workers sit at home and, at the end of the month, receive wages for the work they didn't do, no longer exists. Below are the contributions of this study:

- The system eliminates cheating where someone can claim he came to work whereas he does not but might have connived with another employee who will write his name, sign in and sign out for him and at the end of the day, such employee will be paid fully for what he did not do. Such issue of paying ghost workers is very rampant and if not checked can lead to the collapse of an organisation. With the level of unemployment in the country, there should be measures to protect the few firms that are still running and employing labour.
- It prevents time cheating where an employee who only works for a few hours in a day can claim a full day wage, all because he altered the attendance register to

his favour.

- It can be used to calculate accurate overtime pay for workers so that an employee who does not work overtime will not claim overtime pay at the end of the month just because the system can be manipulated.
- It prevents time wastage where employees queue behind each other to fill and sign the attendance register. A lot of time is wasted in the process which in turn affects their productive hours because of the delay in filling and signing of the attendance register.
- It provides a reliable system of attendance that is storable and information can be retrieved at any point in time as damage to the hard cover can damage a record of many years since it is not electronic where records can be backed up and kept in different storage devices and different locations, it produces only one copy which can be easily damaged either to miss handling where the pages begin to tear off or if there is a fire outbreak.

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